

THE CONTENT OF MATERIALS FOR SEMICONDUCTORS AND THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR SELECTION

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the problems to be solved in creating the content of semiconductor materials, the objectives of effective use of selected materials in the learning process, didactic requirements to materials, recommended methods of teaching selected materials on semiconductors, the structure and summary of selected materials on semiconductors.

It is known from the analysis of educational-methodical, didactic, scientific literature on the content of materials on semiconductors and the principles of their selection that the use of these materials in the educational process provides ample opportunities for improving the content and quality of educational work.

1. The following problems should be solved when creating the content of semiconductor materials:
 1. To determine what traditional, non-traditional methods of using selected materials in lectures and laboratory work in the formation of the content of selected materials on semiconductors and

increase the effectiveness of their teaching.

2. Activation of independent and creative thinking, cognitive abilities, logical observation on the content of selected materials on semiconductors.
3. Development of teaching methods on the content of selected materials on semiconductors.
5. The effective use of selected semiconductor materials in the learning process means the following objectives:
 1. The selected materials on semiconductors meet the

requirements of the curriculum and program, ie help students to master them without difficulty, more precisely, without weight.

7. 2. Selected materials on semiconductors in students to form a scientific worldview in them.
8. 3. To develop students' independent and creative thinking in selected materials on semiconductors.
9. 4. To develop students' abstract thinking, logical observation of selected materials on semiconductors.
10. 5. To be able to apply in practice the theoretical knowledge, practical skills and abilities acquired by students on selected materials on semiconductors.
11. 6. The use of selected materials on semiconductors in the educational process should be purposeful and planned, to identify and select the necessary psychological and pedagogical conditions.
12. The following didactic requirements can be set for the selected materials for semiconductors:
 13. 1. The content of selected materials for semiconductors must meet didactic and methodological requirements.
 14. 2. The content of selected materials on semiconductors should be expressed in a simple, concise, concise and logically complete text.
 15. 3. The content of the selected materials on semiconductors and the facts in them must be true.

16. 4. Selected materials and test questions for semiconductors should be clear and understandable.

The practical results of theoretical and pedagogical experimental work on the formation of the content of selected materials on semiconductors and the methodology of their teaching must be subject to the obtained scientific conclusions and recommendations:

1. The selected materials on semiconductors are included in the concept of physics, the State educational standard, the program and the curriculum.

2. The selected materials for semiconductors meet the modern development of science, technology and production.

3. Non-duplication of selected materials for semiconductors.

4. Selected materials on semiconductors should not be unfamiliar to students, difficult terms.

Based on the above considerations, it is advisable to acquaint students with the content of selected materials on semiconductors in lectures and laboratory classes.

We recommend the following teaching methods to test the selected materials on semiconductors in the pedagogical experimental process:

1. Selection of the content of materials for semiconductors.

2. Asking questions about the content of selected materials for semiconductors.

3. Appropriate use of modern, innovative teaching methods in solving problems.

4. Ultimately, the problems are solved, the goal is achieved.

The structure and summary of the selected materials for semiconductors are given in Table 2.

Table 2

S/n	Selected topics on semiconductor topics	Keywords	Test questions
1.	Electric current in semiconductors. Semiconductor types and their types.	Semiconductor, hollow, single crystal, polycrystalline, elemental semiconductors, binary compound semiconductors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What types of solids are divided according to their electrical conductivity? 2. What substances are called semiconductors? 3. How is electricity generated in semiconductors? 4. What are the properties of semiconductors? 5. What charges are involved in the formation of electric current in semiconductors? 6. What types of semiconductors are divided according to the structure, composition and electrical conductivity of the crystal lattice? 7. How is the electrical conductivity of semiconductors related to external influences?
2.	Specific and mixed conductivity in semiconductors. Zone theory in semiconductors.	<i>p-type semiconductor, n-type semiconductor, donor and acceptor levels</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What semiconductor is called a special semiconductor? 2. Which semiconductor is called a mixed semiconductor?
3.	Electronic cavity transition. Semiconductor diodes and their types	<i>p-n-junction, shielding layer, semiconductor diode, low frequency rectifying diode, pulsed diodes, ultra high frequency diodes,</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How is the electron-cavity transition formed? 2. What device is called a semiconductor diode? 3. How is the VAX of a semiconductor diode obtained? 4. What types of semiconductor diodes are there? 5. What functions do semiconductor diodes perform?

		<i>Schottky diodes, stablitrion, tunnel diodes, varicaps</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. What are the purposes of semiconductor diodes? 7. What are the capabilities of semiconductor diodes? 8. What are the disadvantages of semiconductor diodes?
4	Semiconductor transistors and their types	Semiconductor transistors, bipolar transistors, field-effect transistors, amplifiers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What devices are called semiconductor transistors? 2. What types of semiconductor transistors are there? 3. What is the structure of a bipolar transistor? 4. What functions does a bipolar transistor perform and for what purposes is it used? 5. What is the structure of field-effect transistors? 6. What functions do field-effect transistors perform and for what purposes are they used?

This table of structure and content provides opportunities for section topics,

lesson planning, learning process planning, and independent, thorough, and in-depth study of topics by students.

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